

Alternative ways of European participatory organic fruit breeding projects

DIVERSIFRUIT

InnOBreed

Funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme of the European Union under grant agreement No 101061028

CRA-W

The Walloon Agricultural Research Centre (CRA-W) is a public regional institution developing research programs in agriculture, horticulture and forestry. One of its missions is to safeguard, evaluate and promote the use of the large diversity of its regional fruit tree genetic resources. The collection program started in 1975, and since then the main objective has been to evaluate this large fruit tree collection for its disease tolerance to point out the best performing old varieties and making use of it by releasing the more robust and disease tolerant fruit tree cultivars through a network of SME nurseries. The CRA-W's role is to contribute to the transfer of knowledge and experience on regional diversity of fruit genetic resources, to build long-term conservation actions with the public, to improve public awareness on this topic by enabling the discovery of its richness, and finally, to promote local economic activities based on non-sprayed agroecosystems and various quality fruit products (fresh and processed).

One of the primary goals of the **Diversifruits association** is to unite citizens and stakeholders around the challenges of safeguarding and promoting the uses of our large diversity of fruit tree heritage (pome fruit, stone fruit, small fruits and berries) and to promote the plantation of small or larger unsprayed orchards (garden trees, espaliers, orchard meadows, agroforestry, ...). Another task of the association is to collaborate with CRA-W and the 'Walloon Federation of Natural Parks' in the coordination and animation of a multi-site network of regional repository orchards. This task is performed thanks to the financial support of the Walloon Region. The association is also devoted to promoting economic activities related to fruit heritage from old and new orchard meadows in Belgium. In this way, one of Diversifruits' and CRA-W's partner projects – '**Wal4Fruits**' - supports the development of the economic sector on the downstream side of local enterprises by stimulating the marketing of fruit in accordance with the regional Differentiated Quality standard. **Wal4fruits** also promotes the diversification of orchard production via the implementation of new types of multi-fruit hedges.

DIVERSIFRUITS association

“Everything started with a small group of enthusiastic amateurs and professionals motivated by the preservation of the fruit tree heritage and inspired by the preservation work started and developed at the CRA-W since 1975”.

In 2018, the non-profit organization Diversifruits was established from this initiative under the impetus of the CRA-W and the ‘Walloon Federation of Natural Parks’. The operation of the association is based on a core of volunteer administrators, supported by volunteers and two project managers, that are financed through public funding. The Diversifruits association is now gathering around 150 members that reunite twice a year on networking days. It also proposes around 70 activities per year including trainings, conferences, awareness-raising stands, etc., for a large audience including professionals.

One of the social innovations comes from the fact that Diversifruits acts in a multiactor approach as it is a catalyser between research, nurseries, small companies specialised in the planting and management of high-stem standard trees orchards, livestock farmers, fruit processors and consumers.

In 2023, Diversifruits created, through “Wal4Fruit”, the quality label “Vergers Vivants” – Fruits certified from non-sprayed orchard meadows”. This label aims to generate cohesion between growers and encourage fair remuneration for their productions. This label is officially recognized by the Walloon Region, which means that the producers can benefit from certification assistance and visibility via the Walloon Agency for the Promotion of Quality Agriculture (APAQ-W). This innovative approach is promoting the use of local and more robust fruit varieties. Indeed, the “Vergers Vivants” label promotes the production of fruit (apples, pears, plums, cherries, walnuts, chestnuts) from non-sprayed high-stem orchards. It also covers the processed products made from these fruits. To enable fruit to be produced without the help of plant protection products, a global approach integrating many levels is required. The management of the herbaceous layer, the test and choice of more robust and disease tolerant varieties and rootstocks, the orchard design and maintenance and finally the improvement of the functional diversity are examples of parameters that can be tuned to influence the overall health of a non-sprayed orchard.

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, the Diversifruits is part of the InnOBreed project as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

As case study and stakeholder, Diversifruits could make profit of the project InnOBreed by being included in a European network of organizations with similar objectives and complementary know and experience to share. On other hand, the InnOBreed project could learn from them how is developing a functional multi actor approach, how to manage standard trees and how to develop economic activities with original more robust old fruit varieties in non-sprayed orchard meadows.

You can find more information about DIVERSIFRUITs here:
<https://www.diversifruits.be/>

For further details, contact Marc Lateur (CRA-W):
m.lateur@cra.wallonie.be